

BENEFITS INTEGRATING OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CLASSROOM.

Akhmedova Nodima Izzatullo qizi

Abstract This article provides information about innovative technologies and clarifies benefits of integration of innovative technologies in the classroom. Also, how important using them, is discussed. Listserv, Power Points, Internet Homework Assignments, Online grading Systems, Classroom Tablets programs are given as examples. Moreover, technological integration is explained in this article.

Key words: innovative, technology, integration, classroom, Listserv, Power Points, Internet Homework, Assignments, Online grading Systems, Classroom tablets, program, Microsoft Office, Google Drive, aspect.

Nowadays, science and technology are developing rapidly. The importance of innovative technologies in any aspect of life is incomparable. The importance of innovative technologies in education business and other such wide-ranging fields is increasing day by day. Especially in the field of education, its contribution is becoming noticeable. Achievements in the field of education are considered one of the necessary factors for the development of every country. It should meet the rapidly changing and globalizing world standards as well as being stable and perfect in all aspects. This requires a flexible, consistent and expanded learning process. therefore, teachers, professors and researchers should constantly update the theory and practice of teaching in order to provide sufficient knowledge to students and young people and make them masters of their work in the future. Teaching students well and making them aware of the benefits of innovative thinking will instill in them a passion for learning and provide them with the tools they need to succeed in an age of innovative technology. Furthermore, thanks to innovative technologies, it is easier to find and share the necessary information, and this situation indicates how

necessary it is to use them in the teaching process. Technological devices such as smartphones, tablets, laptops and other devices have already become an integral part of the lives of teachers, students and students. The role of innovative technological tools in organizing the learning process effectively and interestingly for pupils and students is incomparable. Also, the use of such technologies, including power point, interactive games, giving homework via the Internet, online evaluation systems, improves the quality of education, and the use of such technologies and the involvement of students creates the integration of technologies in the classroom and creates individual learning methods for them according to the abilities and needs of students. They are also improving their performance on district benchmarks. It is believed that technology makes learning interesting, enjoyable, and interactive. Learners love to learn by doing, interacting, and discovering.

Using technology in classrooms has the potential to create increased student motivation, increased social interactions, positive outcomes, enhanced student learning, and enhanced student engagement.

In most cases, teachers can achieve effective teaching process when using innovative technologies in the classroom. When innovative technologies are applied to education, they have both positive and negative aspects. Their negative aspects are seen as a distraction to users, but the positives of using technology in the classroom outweigh the negatives if the technology is integrated into the classroom with controlled or assessed procedures.

Student activation. Active participation of students in the lesson is a key part of any curriculum. Whether students are working independently or collaboratively, technology provides this opportunity because it is interactive.

It helps students with different **learning styles**. All students have different learning abilities. Technology helps teachers to choose learning materials based on students' level of knowledge acquisition. Using technology, students can work according to their level.

Preparing students for life skills. Quick reference to innovative technologies in everyday life turned it into a unique form of literacy. Many industries use at least one aspect of Microsoft Office or Google Drive every day. Balance budgets in spreadsheets, create presentations or slideshows, or attach documents to email to convey important information. giving students the opportunity to teach and improve these skills prepares them for life outside the classroom. Below are some innovative technological tools.

Listserv	Programs such as listserv allow parents to manage and organize e-mail messages. Parents can be informed about the various announcements in the educational institutions where their children are studying and about the level of learning of their children.
Tablets	In classrooms equipped with tablets, students and teachers are provided with a number of conveniences. Teachers can work one-on-one with students and observe how active each student is during the lesson.
Online grading systems	are done through PowerSchool or daily com programs. and this, in turn, helps to improve the communication between the administrator, teacher, student and parents, which is the main element of education. Through these programs, teachers have the opportunity to evaluate students and analyze student attendance.
Internet homework assignments	is done through educational platforms such as Blackboard Brightspace and Moodle. This type of teaching is a method of integration. Easy access to assignments keeps students engaged and organized. Also, online literature discussions can create a sense of community and foster positive social interaction.

Power Points	power point presentations allow students to focus on lessons and create an interactive environment in the classroom. by using this program, teachers can enrich the topics they want to explain with graphics and marked information, as well as video links. Also, giving students a task to prepare a graph or slide related to the given topic ensures their active participation in the lesson process and develops their ability to work independently or as a team.
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In conclusion, it is worth saying that the use of integration of innovative technologies in the field of education not only improves the quality of education, but also improves communication between employees of educational institutions and parents. Moreover, the role of innovative technologies in the success in the field of education is incomparable. The application of innovative technologies to education has discovered new effective methods of teaching and learning for professors, teachers and students.

Reference

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3. Courduff, J. (2011). One size never fits all: Tech integration for special needs. *Learning & Leading With Technology*, 38(8), 16-19.

Useful sites

1. <https://drexel.edu/soe/resources/student-teaching/advice/how-to-use-technology-in-the-classroom/>

2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286476273_Educational_innovation_and_technology_A_need_for_integration
3. <https://cehs.usu.edu/itls/files/course-syllabi/5500-technology-integration-innovation.pdf>
4. https://www.westpoint.edu/sites/default/files/inlineimages/centers_research/center_for_teching_excellence/PDFs/mtp_project_papers/Chung_07.pdf